

What Tree for Each Place in Agroforestry for Broadleaves

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Silvopastoral systems established under *Prunus avium* L. in Galicia (NW Spain).

Broadleaves can have leaves that fall down dry or stay in the tree during the winter time attending to the edaphoclimatic conditions. For example Atlantic broadleaves (i.e. *Quercus robur* or *Quercus petraea* (the most widespread broadleaf species in Europe)) are usually without leaves during the winter time, while those in the Mediterranean remain in the tree due to the high energy cost associated with the leaves production during the spring in difficult weather (for example: *Quercus ilex* or *Quercus suber*) whose leaves are usually by farmers to feed animals during the summer period to overcome the summer drought. Others *Quercus* have an intermediate behaviour with leaves dying in winter but kept in the tree until the next spring (i.e *Quercus rotundifolia*). This behaviour changes the soil carbon storage, being it higher in the case of Atlantic broadleaves that are benefited from the fertility that the own tree generates compared with more Mediterranean trees. However, *Quercus spp* are usually compatible with agroforestry systems if tree density is small to allow light to reach the understory. There are also other type of broadleaves linked to timber production like Birch, Walnut or Cherry. Birch is well known for being an intermediate growing species specially suitable for obtaining wood in combination with *Pinus sylvestris*, being an excellent pioneer species able to improve the soil characteristics that can be uses as a fodder. On the opposite site, species like walnut, chestnut or cherry are high value tree species that can be considered as fruit or timber trees. Recently, genetic improvements allows to select trees for each of the fruit or timber purposes that does not to make them compatible. Walnut is more compatible with chestnut because the former is usually with a later leaves sprout, making walnut a species highly compatible with the vegetable or the horticulture or pasture growth during the winter time.

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